

The Technology Singularity

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Kurzweil (1999) predicted that computers would pass the Turing test by 2029. At the time many felt that he was being over optimistic, but now many consider that the Turing test has already been passed. Kurzweil also suggested, in 2005, that we would reach a technology singularity by 2045, a point in time at which machines would start to accelerate their own development and rapidly grow in capability taking them far beyond the realm of human comprehension. Kurzweil was not the first to suggest that the machines we create will destroy us, but Kurzweil generated significant debate by presenting a timeline based on well-established technology trends and information processing capacity.

The Turing test, as posed by Turing, involves expert assessment of a transcript of an exchange between two parties. Jannai et al. (2023) adopt a formulation which does away with the experts and takes the assessment of those taking part in conversations with results that indicate that ChatGPT is almost indistinguishable from humans for many test participants.

Since the launch of ChatGPT in November 2022, the pace of change in computer technology, societal applications, and societal perceptions has quickened. The pace of change, and the forces driving it, have led some, such as Rakish Malik (2024), to suggest that we have passed the event horizon of Ray Kurzweil's singularity.

It seems almost disrespectful to call the new devices computers: the difference between today's machines and those that Turing worked with could be compared to the gulf in intellectual capacity between the first mammals and Homo Sapiens. Kurzweil's concept of the singularity is neutral from a value perspective: some fear that it could lead to a dystopian future in which humanity is wiped out or forever enslaved while others believe it opens a utopian prospect of luxury for all. Philosopher John Gray (2023) sees it as an evolutionary step in which humankind, defeated by its own frailties, is overtaken by a superior form of life.

Malik's suggestion that we have passed the event horizon is related to the fact that machine aided design and production processes are accelerating the rate at which new technology is launched, thus accelerating the speed at which machine capabilities grow.

The concept of an event horizon¹ originates from Einstein's theory of General Relativity. The event horizon marks a critical point in the system, a point of no return: but students

¹ The term was coined by Wolfgang Rindler in 1950.

of physics will know that observers passing through an event horizon would not necessarily know what was happening.

Campbell (1932) imagined the technological singularity as revealing itself in a literal flash when the all-powerful computer unleashes a lightning bolt to protect its power supply.

The reality we face is rather different. At a purely instrumental level we know how to switch off computers, just as we know how to leave oil in the ground, how to leave land alone so that ecosystems can survive.

The critical question is whether we have the capacity to collectively change from a path which is heading for destruction.

The specifics of the threats from the climate crisis, from thinking machines, and from the collapse in biodiversity are all very different, but the same question lies at the heart of all these problems: can we act collectively to avert the impending crisis?

References

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